

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
КЛИНИК ТИББИЁТ
АХБОРОТНОМАСИ**

**BULLETIN OF FUNDAMENTAL
AND CLINIC MEDICINE**

2026, №5 (25)

МИНИСТЕРСТВО ЗДРАВООХРАНЕНИЯ
РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН

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**ВЕСТНИК ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНОЙ И
КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

Научный журнал по фундаментальным
и клиническим проблемам медицины,
основанный в 2022 году Бухарским государственным
медицинским институтом имени Абу Али ибн Сино.
Периодичность издания - один раз в месяц.

Главный редактор – Ш.Ж. ТЕШАЕВ

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2026, № 5 (25)

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О журнале

*Журнал зарегистрирован
в Управлении печати и информации
Бухарской области
№ 1640 от 28 мая 2022 года.*

*Журнал внесен в список
утвержденный приказом № 370/б
от 8 мая 2025 года реестром ВАК
в раздел медицинских наук.*

Отпечатано в типографии ООО
“Шарк-Бухоро”. г. Бухара,
ул. Ўзбекистон Мустақиллиги, 70/2.

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**EARLY DIAGNOSIS OF SECONDARY LEGS SYNDROME, TAKING INTO ACCOUNT
CLINICAL AND NEUROPHYSIOLOGICAL PARAMETERS****Ismati Z.O., Djurabekova A.T.**

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Resume. The article discusses the possibilities of early diagnosis of secondary restless legs syndrome based on a comprehensive assessment of clinical and neurophysiological parameters. The main symptoms and characteristics of the disease's progression are analyzed. It is demonstrated that combining clinical data with instrumental diagnostic results improves the accuracy and timeliness of syndrome detection, facilitating the selection of optimal treatment strategies and improving patients' quality of life.

Key words: restless legs syndrome, IRLS, PSQI, Epworth scale, immobilization suggestion test, polysomnography, electroneuromyography.

**КЛИНИК-НЕЙРОФИЗИОЛОГИК КЎРСАТКИЧЛАРНИ ҲИСОБГА ОЛГАН ҲОЛДА
ИККИЛАМЧИ ОЁҚ СИНДРОМИНИ ЭРТА ТАШХИСЛАШ****Исматӣ З.О., Джурабекова А.Т.**

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Резюме. Мақолада клиник ва нейрoфизиологик кўрсаткичларни комплекс баҳолаш асосида иккиламчи безовта оёқлар синдромини эрта ташхислаш имкониятлари кўриб чиқилади. Касалликнинг асосий белгилари, кечии хусусиятлари таҳлил қилинган. Клиник маълумотларни инструментал диагностика натижалари билан уйғунлаштириши синдромни аниқлашнинг аниқлиги ва ўз вақтидалигини ошириши, бу эса оптимал даволаш тактикасини танлашга ва беморларнинг ҳаёт сифатини яхшилашга ёрдам бериши кўрсатилган.

Калит сўзлар: безовта оёқлар синдроми, ИРЛС, ПСҚИ, Эпворт шкаласи, тавсия этилган им- мобилизация тести, полисомнография, электронейромиография.

**РАННЯЯ ДИАГНОСТИКА ВТОРИЧНОГО СИНДРОМА НОГ С УЧЕТОМ КЛИНИКО-
НЕЙРОФИЗИОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ПАРАМЕТРОВ****Исматӣ З.О., Джурабекова А.Т.**

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Резюме. В статье рассматриваются возможности ранней диагностики вторичного синдрома беспокойных ног на основе комплексной оценки клинических и нейрoфизиологических параметров. Проанализированы основные симптомы, особенности течения заболевания. Показано, что сочетание клинических данных с результатами инструментальной диагностики позволяет повысить точность и своевременность выявления синдрома, что способствует выбору оптимальной тактики лечения и улучшению качества жизни пациентов.

Ключевые слова: синдром беспокойных ног, IRLS, PSQI, шкала Эпворта, тест предложенной иммобилизации, полисомнография, электронейромиография.

Today, restless legs syndrome (RLS) is a widespread neurosensory disorder that significantly reduces quality of life and remains a serious medical and social problem. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), the prevalence of restless legs syndrome among the adult population ranges from 5% to 15%, and the pathology primarily develops in women and the elderly. Despite the development and continuous improvement of therapeutic and preventive measures, the issue of early diagnosis, adequate and effective treatment of secondary restless legs syndrome remains open, which requires further study of this problem.

Research by global and domestic scientists has proven that the global burden of restless legs syndrome is important not only for neurology but for healthcare as a whole. It has been established that the global prevalence of this disease is 7.12% among adults aged 20–79, accounting for 356 million of all cases [4,13]. At the same time, it has been proven that the primary component of this disorder is sleep disorders [12, 7, 15]. According to a global report, restless legs syndrome is the fourth leading cause of insomnia.

Currently, significant attention is paid to studying the pathophysiological mechanisms of BOS development, which are hypothesized to be based on regional iron deficiency in the brain and/or specific genetic factors that disrupt dopamine neurotransmission in the subcortical regions of the brain [5,14], as well as a

pathogenetic link between thyroid hormones and the onset of RLS [1].

In-depth research into pathophysiology has allowed scientists to develop diagnostic criteria [3]. However, despite numerous studies on the fundamental principles of diagnosis and differential diagnosis of secondary restless legs syndrome, the timely detection of signs of SBS remains a problem for many specialists. In this regard, the search for new approaches to early differential diagnosis of this disease is becoming a priority area of further scientific research.

The aim is to evaluate clinical, neurophysiological, and laboratory criteria for the early diagnosis of restless legs syndrome.

Materials and methods. The basis of the study was a prospective study using clinical-neurological, neurophysiological, laboratory, and statistical research methods. The study included 161 individuals, including 109 patients with secondary restless legs syndrome aged 20-75 years (mean age 55.55 ± 8.69 years; men - 38.5% (n=42) and women - 61.5% (n=67)), as well as 52 practically healthy individuals comparable in age and gender.

During the first stage of the examination, an anamnesis was collected to determine the plan of further action. To assess the severity of the condition of patients with RLS, the IRLS scale was used; to determine the presence of a depressive disorder, patients were asked to complete the Center for the Epidemiological Study of Depression questionnaire (CES-D); and to assess sleep quality, the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Questionnaire (PSQI). Daytime sleepiness was also assessed using the Epworth scale. Patients who did not meet all the main criteria for the disease were subjected to the proposed immobilization test, electroneuromyography, and polysomnography.

All obtained data were statistically processed using Microsoft Excel 16, SPSS, and Anova software packages.

Results of the research. When a thorough medical history was collected, it was established that the average age of disease onset was 43.24 ± 3.81 years. In 100% of patients, the main symptom was unpleasant sensations in the legs, which appeared mainly at rest and disappeared during active movements. Patients described these sensations as pain in 55.9% of cases, stinging and ants in 30.3%, twisting in 34.9%, electric shock in 14.7%, and tension in 18.3% (fig.1). This sensory-motor discomfort was localized in 94.5% of cases in the lower leg, 47.7% in the foot, 26.6% in the thigh, and 9.2% in the arms (fig.2).

Figure 1. Main clinical manifestations of RLS

Figure 2. Location of sensory-motor discomfort

The latent period of the desire to act at rest was observed in 70.6% of cases immediately, in 22.9% after 5–10 minutes, and in 6.4% after 20–30 minutes. At the same time, 67.9% of patients felt complete relief after moving their legs, 27.5% felt partial relief, and 4.6% of patients experienced no relief. Symptoms most

frequently manifested in the evening and night hours in 86.2% (n=94), and in the daytime in 13.8% (n=15), with the disease intermittent in 80.7% of cases and progressive in 19.3% (fig.3).

Figure 3. Analysis of the latent period of movement urge and feeling of relief

In accordance with the tasks set at the next stage, we also conducted an assessment of the severity of the disease, sleep quality, daytime sleepiness, and the severity of depression. When assessing the severity of clinical manifestations using the IRLS scale, the mild stage of the disease was identified in 17.4% (n=19) of all examined patients, the moderate stage in 60.6%, and the severe stage in 22%.

To assess sleep quality, we used the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Assessment Scale, which includes 7 parameters such as sleep quality, sleep time, duration, effectiveness, sleep disturbance, sleep medication intake, and daytime dysfunction. The survey results showed that 37.6% of respondents reported moderate sleep disturbances, 47.7% experienced severe sleep disturbances, and 14.7% reported no sleep disturbances.

When assessing daytime sleepiness using the Epworth scale, moderate sleepiness was observed in 42.2% of cases, while 46.8% of all patients suffered from pathological sleepiness. We did not find problems with daytime sleepiness in only 11% of patients.

When assessing the severity of depression, according to the CES-D questionnaire results, a mild degree of depression was identified in 39.4% of patients, and a moderate degree of depressive disorders in 11.9%. In 48.6% of patients, no signs of depression were observed. There is a direct moderate correlation between the severity of depressive disorders and the severity of clinical manifestations ($r=0.51$), which proves the influence of the syndrome's development on the exacerbation of emotional disorders.

Patients were also subjected to the proposed immobilization test, at the end of which 29.88 cyclic limb movements were recorded.

Given that not all mandatory signs were manifested in all patients, we conducted a polysomnographic examination (fig.4). The results of the study showed that 36.4% of patients in the main group suffered from nighttime obstructive apnea of a mild degree. Absolutely all patients woke up from 1 to 4 times a night. In the control group, isolated cases were observed. At the same time, saturation in the study group was 1.6% lower and showed no significant differences compared to the control group. For us, sleep latency, sleep effectiveness, and the index of periodic limb movements were of great diagnostic importance. Thus, patients in the main group slept 3.8 times longer, and sleep efficiency was 15.7% lower than in the control group. Sleep disturbances, as a rule, were exacerbated by periodic leg movements, which was confirmed by a 90-fold increase from the norm. The EEG activation index, which was 57% higher than in healthy individuals, was also significant for conducting the proposed mobilization test.

Electroneuromyography was also included in the study (fig.5). We studied the pulse conduction velocity along n.suralis and n.tibialis, the M-response amplitude, the excitability threshold, and the ENMG curve amplitude. The analysis results showed significant differences between the compared groups. Thus, the amplitude of the M-response with NS in the main group of patients was significantly lower by 64%, SRV by 33%, the amplitude of the ENMG curve by 19%, and the excitability threshold was significantly higher by 48%. As a result of the study of NT, a significant decrease in M-response amplitude indicators by 63%, ENMG curve amplitude by 19%, and excitability threshold by 50% was identified, respectively.

Figure 4. Results of polysomnography

Figure 5. Analysis of the result of electroneuromyography

Conclusion: 1. Early diagnosis of secondary restless legs syndrome is possible with a comprehensive analysis of clinical manifestations and neurophysiological parameters. 2. The use of neurophysiological methods allows us to identify hidden dysfunctions of the nervous system even at the preclinical stages of the disease. 3. Taking into account concomitant pathologies and risk factors plays a key role in the timely recognition of the secondary form of the syndrome. 4. A combined diagnostic approach increases the accuracy of diagnosis and reduces the likelihood of diagnostic errors. 5. Timely detection of the disease contributes to a more effective choice of treatment tactics and an improvement in the quality of life of patients.

Thus, the results obtained indicate the high informativeness of diagnostic methods such as polysomnography and electroneuromyography, which allow for not only differential diagnosis but also early detection of the disease

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For citation: Ismati Z.O., Djurabekova A.T. Early diagnosis of secondary legs syndrome, taking into account clinical and neurophysiological parameters // *Bulletin of Fundamental and Clinic Medicine*. – 2026. – № 5(25). – P. 128–132. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20034542>